

**PHOTOCATALYTIC DEGRADATION OF PURPURIN DYE VIA PHOTOLYSIS AND
PHOTOCATALYSIS USING TITANIUM OXIDE AS A NANOPARTICLE**

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CERTIFICATION

This is to certify that this project report was written by **OKEWALE DAMILARE JOHN** with the Matric number, **CHE/2018/1083** of the Department of Chemistry, Faculty of science, Federal University Oye Ekiti, Ekiti State, Nigeria under the supervision of **DR. O.S AYANDA**

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DEDICATION

This report is dedicated to the Almighty God, for His loving kindness over my life, for his favor, wisdom and mercy since the beginning of my seminar and to my parents for their parental Guidance and financial support

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

I would like to use this opportunity to express my sincere gratitude to God for his mercy and faithfulness. Also, I am grateful to my parents for their parental and financial support, love, care and even spiritual intervention. To my supervisor, Dr. O.S AYANDA, appreciation goes to him for his assistance and mentorship, to DR. (MRS) AREMU for her guidance which has been a great help since the beginning of this piece, to all the lecturers in the department of CHEMISTRY and to my parents and siblings. I am grateful. Lastly, appreciation goes to all my friends and colleagues who aided in one way or the other throughout the journey.

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ABSTRACT

Dyeing is the process of coloring organic materials, such as fabrics, paper, food, hair, and pharmaceuticals, with colored compounds. Photocatalytic degradation of dye is a method of controlling water pollution. In this research the efficiency of the synthesized titanium oxide nanoparticle a photocatalyst for the degradation of purpurin dye in an aqueous solution was investigated. The nanoparticles are used as catalyst to help in the breaking down of dye molecules when exposed to light. Titanium oxide nanocomposites have been used not only in the field of diverse advanced catalytic technologies and sensors but also in the field of energy storage. Photolysis and photocatalysis was carried out on purpurin dye wastewater considering the effect of time, concentration, pH, and nanodosage. The % of degradation result was compared when titanium oxide was used during photocatalysis and when photolysis was carried out considering (effect of time, pH, and concentration). The result for photolysis was better than that of photocatalysis. This research contributes to the field of environment remediation by exploring an innovative approach for the removal of dye contaminants from water systems.

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CHAPTER ONE

1.0 DYES

Dyeing is the process of coloring organic materials, such as fabrics, paper, food, hair, and pharmaceuticals, with colored compounds. Dyes and pigments are the two categories of organic colorants based on their solubility. (Kumar *et al.*, 2021). The main difference is that pigments cannot be dissolved in either water or an organic solvent, whereas dyes can. Dyeing is done with dyes on substrates that they are suited for. (Toivola *et al.*, 2009). Any polymeric substrate can be colored using pigments, although this process differs greatly from dyeing in that surface-only coloring is done unless the pigment is mixed with the polymer before to the production of fiber or molded items.

1.1 HISTORY OF DYE

Dyeing wool cloth, 1482: from a French translation of Bartolomeus Anglicus throughout history, people have dyed their textiles using common, locally accessible materials. Scarce dyestuffs that produced brilliant and permanent colors, such as the natural invertebrate dyes Tyrian purple and crimson kermes, were highly prized luxury items in the ancient and medieval world. In the economies of Asia and Europe, plant-based dyes like wood, indigo, saffron, and madder played a significant role in trade. In order to manage the color absorption in pieced-dyed cloth, patterned fabrics were created throughout Asia and Africa employing resist dyeing processes. The Spanish treasure voyages brought dyestuffs from the New World, such as cochineal and logwood, to Europe, and colonists brought dyestuffs from Europe to America (Adrosko and Rita, 1971). In a prehistoric cave in the Republic of Georgia that dates to 36,000 BC, dyed flax fibers have been discovered (Balter *et al.*, 2009). Dyeing has been a common practice for more than 5,000 years, especially in India and Phoenicia, according to archeological data. Early dyes had little to no processing and were derived from animal, vegetable, or mineral sources. The plant kingdom has historically been the largest

source of dyes, particularly from roots, berries, bark, leaves, and wood, however only a small number of these are employed commercially. J. Pullar and Sons carried out early industrialization in Scotland. (Puller, 1803). William Henry Perkin made the accidental discovery of mauve, the first synthetic dye, in 1856. Synthetic dyes and organic chemistry in general saw a boom following the discovery of mauveine. Fuchsine, Safranine, and Induline were some of the other aniline colors that came after. Since then, countless numbers of synthetic colors have been created. (Zollinger *et al.*, 2003). The discovery of mauve also influenced advances in chemotherapy and immunology. In what is now Wuppertal, Germany, the predecessor to Bayer AG was established in 1863. Paul Ehrlich found in 1891 that some organisms or cells selectively absorbed particular colours. Then, he reasoned that, if the dye did not impact other cells, a dose that was sufficiently high could be administered to kill pathogenic germs. The first time a chemical was employed to specifically destroy bacteria in the body was when Ehrlich used it to target syphilis. The plasmodium that causes malaria was also the target of his usage of methylene blue. (Burrows *et al.*, 2009)

1.2 CLASSIFICATIONS OF DYES

The classification of dye is an important aspect of the dye industry, as it helps to categorize and differentiate the various types of dyes based on their physical and chemical properties. The classification of dye is generally based on the source of the dye, the chemical structure of the dye molecule, and the type of fabric or material that the dye is intended to colour.

Figure 1: The schematic diagram of classification of dyes (Shindhal *et al.*, 2021)

1.3 NANOPARTICLES

A particle of matter with a diameter of one to one hundred nanometers (nm) is commonly referred to as a nanoparticle or ultrafine particle. (Vert *et al.*, 2012). When referring to fibers and tubes that are smaller than 100 nm in only two orientations or larger particles up to 500 nm, the phrase is occasionally used. Smaller metal particles are typically referred to as atom clusters at the lowest limit, which is smaller than 1 nm. Because of their smaller size, nanoparticles are typically distinguished from microparticles (1-1000 m), "fine particles" (sized between 100 and 2500 nm), and "coarse particles" (ranging from 2500 to 10,000 nm). In contrast to colloidal particles, which typically range in size from 1 to 1000 nm and are more sensitive to Brownian

motion, they typically do not sediment. Nanoparticles are significantly smaller than the visible light spectrum (400–700 nm), making it impossible to observe them with standard optical microscopes. Instead, they must be viewed with electron microscopes or laser microscopes. For the same reason, suspensions of bigger particles typically reflect some or all transmitted visible light, whereas dispersions of nanoparticles in transparent liquids can be transparent (Chae *et al.*, 2003). Nanoparticle separations from liquids need specific nanofiltration methods since nanoparticles readily pass through ordinary filters, such as ordinary ceramic candles (Sankar *et al.*, 2013). The properties of nanoparticles often differ markedly from those of larger particles of the same substance. Since the typical diameter of an atom is between 0.15 and 0.6 nm, a large fraction of the nanoparticle's material lies within a few atomic diameters of its surface. Therefore, the properties of that surface layer may dominate over those of the bulk material. This effect is particularly strong for nanoparticles dispersed in a medium of different composition since the interactions between the two materials at their interface also become significant. (Silvera *et al.*, 2015)

Figure 2: A crystalline nanoparticle of platinum (Silvera *et al.*, 2015)

1.3.1 TYPES OF NANOPARTICLES

There are five (5) types of nanoparticles which are;

1. Carbon-based nanoparticles

These are nanoscale materials primarily composed of carbon atoms. They encompass various structures like carbon nanotubes, graphene, and fullerenes. These nanoparticles possess exceptional properties, including mechanical strength, electrical conductivity, and chemical reactivity. Their unique characteristics make them important in fields such as nanotechnology, electronics, and materials science. (Dresselhaus *et al.*, 2000)

2. Metallic nanoparticles

These are tiny particles made up of metal atoms at the nanoscale. These nanoparticles exhibit distinct properties due to their small size and high surface area-to-volume ratio, making them valuable in various fields such as catalysis, electronics, and medicine. (Kumar *et al.*, 2018)

3. Ceramic nanoparticles

These are nanoscale materials composed primarily of ceramic compounds. They possess unique properties, including high-temperature stability, hardness, and electrical insulation, making them valuable in applications like advanced ceramics, coatings, and biomedical materials. (Gogotsi *et al.*, 2020)

4. Polymeric nanoparticles

These are minute particles made of polymer materials at the nanoscale. These nanoparticles offer versatile properties, such as controlled drug release, biocompatibility, and tunable mechanical characteristics, making them essential in drug delivery systems, nanomedicine, and materials science. (Zou *et al.*, 2017)

5. Bio-molecules derived nanoparticles

Bio-molecule derived nanoparticles are nanoscale materials created from natural biomolecules like proteins, nucleic acids, or lipids. These nanoparticles are biocompatible and can be tailored for drug delivery, gene therapy, and diagnostic applications due to their inherent biological properties. (Senapati *et al.*, 2018)

1.3.2 USES OF NANOPARTICLES

The range of the application of nanotube is wide across different aspect because of their distinguished properties;

Drug Delivery: Drugs can be encapsulated through the help of nanoparticles, enhances their stability, solubility, and also aims to specific locations in the body. This enhances drug efficacy while reducing side effects (Zhang *et al.*, 2006).

Cancer Therapy: Nanoparticles can be used in the treatment of cancer, in the delivery of therapeutic agents specifically for tumor tissues, reducing damages to cells that are healthy and enhancing the effectiveness of drugs (Dreaden *et al.*, 2012).

Environmental Remediation: The clean-up of the environment can be improved through the help of nanoparticles, such as removing contaminants from soil and water, heavy metals and pollutants, (Alsafran *et al.*, 2023).

Electronics: Nanoparticles can also be used in the electronics industry, improving the performance of electronic devices and enhancing energy efficiency (Nirmal *et al.*, 2013).

Catalysis: Nanoparticles also serve as catalysts during chemical reactions because of their unique catalytic properties and high surface area (Zaera, 2013)

1.3.3 EFFECT OF NANOPARTICLES

Nanoparticles can have a wide range of effects, both positive and negative, depending on their composition, size, and application.

1. **Health Effects:** Some nanoparticles may pose health risks due to their potential toxicity when inhaled or ingested. For instance, certain types of engineered nanoparticles can induce oxidative stress and inflammation in cells. (Oberdorster *et al.*,2005)

2. **Environmental Effects:** Nanoparticles can also impact the environment, affecting aquatic life and terrestrial ecosystems. For example, nanoparticles in sunscreens may harm aquatic organisms. (Mura *et al.*, 2013)
3. **Medical Applications:** Nanoparticles are widely used in medicine for targeted drug delivery, improving the effectiveness of treatments while minimizing side effects. (Singh *et al.*, 2011)
4. **Material Science:** Nanoparticles can enhance material properties like strength, electrical conductivity and catalytic activity. For instance, carbon nanotubes are known for their exceptional mechanical strength and electrical conductivity. (Baughman *et al.*, 2002)
5. **Electronics:** Nanoparticles enable the miniaturization of electronic components, leading to more efficient and powerful devices. [Vaddiradu *et al.*, 2010)
6. **Energy Applications:** Nanoparticles are used to enhance energy storage technologies, such as batteries and supercapacitors, by increasing their capacity and charge/discharge rates. (Wu *et al.*, 2009)
7. **Environmental Remediation:** Nanoparticles can be employed for water purification, removing contaminants like heavy metals and organic pollutants. (Dong *et al.*, 2015)

1.4 ADVANCED OXIDATION PROCESS

Advanced Oxidation Processes (AOPs) are a collection of oxidative water treatment methods that can be applied to the treatment of toxic effluent in industrial settings, healthcare facilities, and wastewater treatment facilities. Advanced oxidation processes (AOPs), which remove contaminants with poor biodegradability or high chemical stability, are rapidly being recognized as a highly competitive water treatment technique. AOPs are effective at converting harmful organic chemicals (such as pharmaceuticals, pesticides, endocrine disruptors, etc.) into biodegradable ones. It is a challenging approach for

treating wastewater, and it may take some time to grasp how it all fits together. There are also a lot of different oxidation processes to choose from, which can be confusing. AOPs are often inexpensive to build but have high operating costs because they require chemical AOPs are often inexpensive to construct but have substantial operational costs because of the energy and chemical requirements (Singh *et al.* 2020). AOPs are frequently utilized as pre-treatments in conjunction with biologic treatment to save costs (Oller *et al.*, 2011)

Ozone degrades through a protracted process when exposed to significant concentrations of hydroxide ions or hydrogen peroxide. UV light can be used as a catalyst to degrade ozone and hydrogen peroxide by using massless photons to dissolve atomic bonds. Additionally, the light can contribute to the accelerated oxidation process by acting as a disinfectant and an oxidizer. Radicals are created when pollutants are broken down into intermediates, which are subsequently broken down even more by leftover radicals and original oxidants. The contaminants are generally broken down into salts, water, and carbon dioxide, which are all simple inorganic compounds. (Barner *et al.*, 1992)

These systems, often referred to as hydroxyl scavengers, are typically used in tertiary treatments and are sensitive to suspended particles and other compounds. These scavengers reduce oxidation efficiency by obstructing UV radiation and reacting with the (OH•) radical over the target molecules. Examples of AOPs; The term "AOPs" is used to describe a wide range of techniques. Some of the most researched processes are listed in the table. Advanced oxidation often takes place in mild conditions (low temperature and pressure) with the use of powerful oxidizing agents like hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂) or ozone (O₃), catalysts (iron ions, electrodes, metal oxides), and irradiation (UV light, solar light, ultrasounds). According to the vast quantity of data accessible in the literature, among the various AOPs available, those powered by light appear to be the most widely used technologies for wastewater treatment (Stasinakis, 2008). The schematic diagram of advance oxidation process can be found below;

Figure 3: Advanced Oxidation Process (Sylwia et al., 2012)

The Advanced Oxidation Process is based in part on chemical and photochemical

processes, including some of the following:

1.4.1 OZONE-BASED AOPS

Ozone interacts with substances containing hydrogen and breaks them down into OH radicals in a sequence of stages. Due to the large concentration of hydroxide ions present, it can only be utilized as an AOP on its own at higher pH values. O₃, which has an oxidation potential of 2.07 V vs. SCE and serves as a secondary oxidizer in the process despite the slower reactions, is a strong oxidant in and of itself. O₃ must be produced locally and used right away if it is employed because of its brief half-life. Furthermore, the creation of bromates molecules, which are extremely hazardous, is conceivable if bromide is one of the contaminants in the wastewater. Direct O₃ oxidation, however, is a selective process that preferentially reacts with ionized and dissociated organic molecules rather than the neutral form, with typical reaction rate constants of $1.0 \times 10^0 - 10^3 \text{M}^{-1} \text{s}^{-1}$ ⁸. In some circumstances, the production of OH• from O₃ serves as the first catalyst for the indiscriminate oxidation (indirect processes). The sophisticated OH• generation has been explained by a variety of intricate mechanisms, and the total response including OH• generation is stated below:

The OH• yield can be greatly increased in the presence of additional oxidants or irradiation. For instance, in the so-called peroxone (O₃/H₂O₂) system, hydroperoxide (HO₂⁻) formed from H₂O₂ decomposition promotes O₃ decomposition and OH• production. (Rizzo *et al.*, 2019)

H₂O₂ is produced as an extra oxidant during the O₃/UV irradiation, largely through O₃ photolysis (Eq. 4).

As a result, three processes, ozonation (Eq. 1), O₃/H₂O₂ (Eq. 2 and 3), and photolysis of H₂O₂ (Eq. 5) are the minimum through which OH can be produced. (Tan *et al.*, 2013)

1.4.2 PHOTOLYSIS

UV is a wavelength of light, not an oxidant in and of itself, but it does transport massless photons to chemical compounds, causing their bonds to be broken fast and easily. UV light is frequently employed as a disinfectant since it has the power to eradicate or stop the growth of a range of infections. But since UV interaction is light-driven, some impurities, including suspended particles, can lessen its effectiveness by preventing it from reaching the intended chemicals. (Ferreira *et al.*, 2021)

In the presence of catalysts or oxidants, photons can start the formation of hydroxyl radicals. Titanium dioxide (TiO_2), a RO-type semiconductor, is the most popular catalyst. In order to create positive holes with an oxidative capacity in the valence band ($h\nu^+_{vb}$) and negative electrons with a reductive capacity at the conduction band (e^-_{cb}), TiO_2 particles must be excited as follows:

These holes and electrons can further combine to generate hydroxyl radicals through the interactions with OH^- , H_2O , and O_2^- at the surface of TiO_2 . (Lee *et al.*, 2002)

In the presence of oxidants like H_2O_2 or O_3 , more $\text{OH}\bullet$ may be produced when exposed to UV rays. For instance, UV radiation can split an H_2O_2 molecule into two $\text{OH}\bullet$.

Additionally, $\text{OH}\bullet$ can also be created at a wavelength lower than 242 nm, possibly through the photolysis of H_2O . (Tan *et al.*, 2013)

1.4.2.1 PHOTO-CATALYSIS

According to Ollis and Al-Ekabi (1993), photocatalytic processes use oxygen as an oxidizing agent and semiconductor metal oxide as a catalyst. There have been numerous catalysts investigated up to this point, but only TiO₂ in the anatase (one of the three crystalline forms of titanium dioxide) form appears to have the most intriguing characteristics, such as high stability, good performance, and low cost (Zhang *et al.*, 1994). The creation of electron-hole pairs after radiation absorption is what starts the photocatalytic reaction.

As a result of the generated electrons' strong reducing power, certain metals and dissolved oxygen can be reduced, resulting in the creation of the superoxide radical ion O₂⁻, while the leftover holes can oxidize adsorbed water or HO• to reactive HO radicals:

Due to the large concentration of H₂O and HO⁻ adsorbed on the particle surface during these reactions, oxidative degradation processes (Andreozzi *et al.*, 1999) place a high priority on them. Some adsorbed substrate can undergo direct electron transfer oxidation:

Unfortunately, a large portion of electron-hole pairs recombine, lowering the quantum yield. The likelihood of using a wavelength from the sun spectrum is emphasized in the majority of research on photo-catalysis. This is only partially accurate, though, because there isn't much overlap between the sun's ground-level absorption spectrum and that of TiO₂ (Andreozzi *et al.*, 1999).

Depending on whether a photocatalytic reaction occurs in a single phase or uses a heterogeneous catalyst like a metal supported catalyst, carbon materials, or a semiconductor like TiO₂, ZnO, or Cds, it can be categorized as either a homogeneous or heterogeneous process. Chemical change resulting from interactions between chemical reagents and target substances characterizes homogeneous processes

(Ribeiro *et al.*, 2015). Hydrogen peroxide (H_2O_2) will break down by ferric (Fe^{2+}) ions present in the aqueous phase, resulting in the generation of hydroxyl radical, making the Photo-Fenton reaction a homogeneous process (Chong *et al.*, 2010).

In a chemical oxidation process known as heterogeneous photo-catalysis, a metal oxide semiconductor is submerged in water and exposed to near UV light, which causes the creation of a free hydroxyl radical (Umar and Aziz, 2013). According to Robert *et al.* (2012), the fundamental tenet of semiconductor photo-catalysis depends on the production of an electron-hole pair following the absorption of a photon with energy equal to or greater than the semiconductor gap. On the surface of the semiconductor, these two extremely reactive substances are involved in a number of oxidative and reductive reactions (Chong *et al.*, 2010).

1.4.3 ULTRASOUND

Ultrasound is a term used in the United States to describe sound waves having a frequency between 20 kHz and 500 MHz. Cavitation bubbles are created when ultrasonic waves travel through a liquid, and their collapse has both physical and chemical repercussions. Due to the greater production of free radicals, chemical ultrasonic effects are particularly dominant at high frequencies. These radicals proceed to the liquid-gas interface where they interact with the organic substrate, or in cases of high concentration, they combine again to create the oxidizing agent H_2O_2 , which facilitates the breakdown of pollutants. (Li *et al.* 2022)

1.4.4 FENTON

The Fenton is a well-known AOP, and reactions involving it involve peroxides (H_2O_2) and Fe^{2+} , which can produce reactive oxygen species that can break down both organic and inorganic materials in aqueous phase. Henry J. Fenton first described the activation of H_2O_2 by ferrous salts for the oxidation of tartaric acid in 1894. Haber and Weiss postulated in 1934 that the Fenton reaction results in the production of $\cdot\text{OH}$. The

oxidation potential of this $\cdot\text{OH}$ is 2.73V. As a result, it is one among the most potent and active oxidants that may be utilized to break down most organic molecules, including developing ones. (Xie et al., 2022)

1.5 TITANIUM OXIDE

Titanium oxide, which can also be called titanium (iv) oxide is the inorganic compound that has the chemical formula TiO_2 . When applied as a pigment, it is known as titanium white. (Van *et al.*, 2016). It is a solid that does not dissolve in water and it is white in color, even though in mineral form it appears as black. When it is used as color for food, it has E number E171. World production in 2014 is over 9 million tonnes. It has been estimated that titanium dioxide is used in two-thirds of all pigments. (Świątczak *et al.*, 2023)

Figure 4: Structure of titanium oxide (Watanabe *et al.*, 1966)

1.5.1 Production of titanium oxide

The five largest TiO₂ pigment processors are in 2019 Cristal Global, Kronos, Chemours, Tronox and Venator (Hayes, 2011). Major coating and painting company end users for pigment grade titanium oxide include Akzo Nobel, PPG Industries, Sherwin Williams, BASF, Kansai Paints and Valspar. Global TiO₂ pigment demand Evolution of the global production of titanium oxide according to process for 2010 was 5.3 Mt with annual growth expected to be about 3–4%. The method of production is determined on the feedstock. Both sulfate and chloride processes produce the titanium oxide pigment in the rutile crystal form, but the Sulfate Process can be adjusted to produce the anatase form. Anatase, being softer, is used in fiber and paper applications. (Gázquez *et al.*, 2021). The Chloride Process is run as a continuous process; The Sulfate Process is run as a batch process.

1.5.1.1 Chloride process

In chloride process, the ore is treated with chlorine and carbon to give titanium tetrachloride, a volatile liquid that is further purified by distillation. The TiCl₄ is treated with oxygen to regenerate chlorine and produce the titanium oxide. (Bordbar *et al.*, 2017)

1.5.1.2 Sulfate process

Chemical manufacturing plants using the sulfate process, require ilmenite concentrate (45–60% TiO₂) or pretreated feedstocks as a suitable source of titanium (Vartiainen 1998) In the sulfate process, ilmenite is treated with sulfuric acid to extract iron (ii) sulfate pentahydrate. The resulting synthetic rutile is further processed according to the specifications of the end user, i.e. pigment grade or otherwise. In another method for the production of synthetic rutile from ilmenite the Becher process first oxidizes the ilmenite as a means to separate the iron component. (Liu *et al.*, 2017)

1.5.1.3 Specialized methods

For specialty applications, TiO₂ films are prepared by various specialized chemistries. Sol-gel routes involve the hydrolysis of titanium alkoxides, such as titanium ethoxide:

This technology is suited for the preparation of films. A related approach that also relies on molecular precursors involves chemical vapor deposition. In this application, the alkoxide is volatilized and then decomposed on contact with a hot surface. (Shugurova *et al.*, 2016)

1.6 AIM AND OBJECTIVES

1.6.1 Aim

The aim of this study is to investigate and compare the effectiveness of photolysis and photocatalysis using titanium oxide nanoparticles for the degradation of purpurin dye from water.

1.6.2 Objectives

The objectives of are as follows;

1. To degrade purpurin dye using synthesized TiO₂ nanoparticle
2. To study the effect of various parameters for the photocatalytic degradation of purpurin dye such as pH, initial concentration of dye and catalyst, and light intensity.

1.7 JUSTIFICATION OF THE STUDY

This study justifies the usage of TiO₂ nanoparticles in the purpurin dye removal process and demonstrates its significance for many purposes. When hazardous purpurin dye is released into the environment, it can lead to significant environmental issues. Purpurin dye is frequently used in the textile industry. The regional approaches to remove the purpurin dye from wastewater (such as chemical oxidation and adsorption) are costly and potentially dangerous. Furthermore, a fantastic alternative technique that is efficient, environmentally safe, and economical is the photocatalytic degradation of the purpurin dye utilizing TiO₂ nanoparticles.

CHAPTER TWO

2.0 LITERATURE REVIEW ON DYE

Studies and researches have been made to improve the availability and sustainable treatment of dyes. Due to the adverse effects caused by the presence of wastewater in the environment and health risk caused to man, various methods and techniques are used in the treatment of wastewater. They include ozonation technology and biological methods, adsorption and photodegradation (Fang *et al.*,2011). Ozonation is a method used in the treatment of wastewater, it is limited in that intermediate with toxicity higher than the parent compound is formed (Dantas *et al.*, 2010). Biological methods treatment process requires long duration (Ingerslev and Halling, 2001). Adsorption is a common method used to remove toxic organic compounds from wastewater. It has a disadvantage in that degradation do not occur as it just involves the accumulation of contaminants from the wastewater to a solid phase (Mendez-Dias *et al.*,2010).

2.1 REVIEWS ON PURPURIN DYE

Purpurin is a natural organic dye that is primarily used as a dye, specifically as a red colorant in inks and textiles. It is found in the root of *Ruba tinctorum*, a plant commonly known as madder. Over the years' research has been conducted on purpurin dye. Wang *et al.*, 2013, studied purpurin dye by applying it on a wound and it resulted in healing by reducing inflammation and stimulating collagen synthesis. Li *et al.*, 2011, studied purpurin dye for curing skin diseases and it was effective in curing diseases like psoriasis, atopic dermatitis, and acne.

Busch *et al.*,2011, studied purpurin dye for the treatment of cancer and it was discovered to have some anti-cancer properties, and it was used to treat cancer and in

photodynamic therapy

2.2 REVIEWS ON PHOTOCATALYTIC DEGRADATION OF PURPURIN DYE

There are many different catalysts that have been studied for the application and degradation efficiency which depend on the reaction condition and the catalyst that was been used. Li *et al.*,2013, studied the photocatalytic degradation of purpurin dye using titanium oxide as a catalyst and it resulted in a 98% degradation efficiency after 90mins of irradiation. Sivakumar *et al.*,2015; Zhang *et al.*, 2016, studied the photocatalytic degradation of purpurin dye using zinc oxide as a catalyst and it resulted in a range of 70% to 98%. Tan *et al.*, 2012, used bismuth vanadate and it was effective in the photocatalytic degradation of purpurin dye achieving a degradation up to 100%

2.3 REVIEWS ON APPLICATION OF TITANIUM OXIDE FOR PURPURIN DYE REMOVAL

In recent years, much attention has been paid by the research community to the simultaneous removal of dyes as well as heavy metals (Louangsouphom *et al.* 2019; de Lima *et al.* 2020; Izzudin *et al.* 2021). This methodology minimizes the processing time, operating cost as well as the use of chemicals in comparison with individual treatment methods. Titanium dioxide was found to be very effective in simultaneous removal of heavy metals and dyes. In some cases, the presence of one pollutant was found to enhance the removal of another pollutant. For instance, the presence of purpurin dye, during the transformation of aqueous metal chromium (iv) to chromium (iii) using titanium dioxide nano-fibre membrane accelerated the removal rate (Zhang *et al.* 2021), and under optimized conditions, the efficacy of hetero-layered titanium dioxide incorporated on layered double hydroxide-molybdenum disulphide nanostructure was recently tested on the removal of organic cations and ionic dyes along with silver and lead ions and found that 97–99% dye removal was achieved (Panchal *et al.* 2021). Simultaneously, due to its excellent affinity and selectivity for heavy metal ions, it rapidly reduced the toxic lead from 10 mg/L to less than 0.8 µg/L and this substrate showed an enormous adsorption capacity of silver (421.88 mg/g).

In recent years, different forms of nano titanium dioxide were used which include one-dimensional nanowire, a nanobelt, two-dimensional nanotubes and nanosheets and three-dimensional nanoparticles as well as nanorods. The major advantages of one-

dimensional nanobelt are lesser number of grain boundaries, fast charge transfer dynamics and high specific surface, which makes nanobelt more attractive (Pang *et al.* 2015). But these issues were resolved by researchers in recent years. For instance, less recombination of electron/hole pairs was observed during the use of novel hybrid bismuth subcarbonate ($\text{Bi}_2\text{O}_2\text{CO}_3$) quantum dot/titanium dioxide nanobelt on the removal of rhodamine blue (Wang *et al.* 2021). The removal efficiency of 95.43% under visible light, which is nine times larger than that of titanium dioxide nanobelts, was observed

CHAPTER THREE

MATERIALS AND METHODS

3.1 MATERIALS AND REAGENTS

The materials used for this experiment includes; UV lamp, UV spectrophotometer, filter paper, tissue, stopwatch, spatula, pH meter, weighing balance, glassware such as beakers, cuvette, volumetric flask purpurin dye, also chemicals with high purity was used for this experiment obtained from the Department of Industrial Chemistry, Federal University Oye Ekiti. The chemicals include HCL, NaOH, titanium oxide (TiO₂), Distilled water is also needed for the experiment.

3.2 SAMPLE PREPARATION

0.05g of purpurin dye was weighed and poured into a 100cm³ volumetric flask; it was filled with water to the mark

3.3 EFFECT OF OPERATING PARAMETERS UNDER PHOTOLYSIS

3.3.1 EFFECT OF TIME

The effect of contact time on the degradation of purpurin dye was investigated. Purpurin dye (50mls) was placed in a beaker and studied using a uv lamp. The time intervals investigated were 10min, 20min, 30min, 40min and 60min. After completion, the solution was analysed using a u/v spectrophotometer at a wavelength of 416nm.

3.3.2 EFFECT OF CONCENTRATION

The effect of concentration on the degradation of purpurin dye was investigated. Purpurin dye (50mls) was placed in a beaker and studied using a uv lamp and this was done for concentration of 100mg/L, 50mg/L, 25mg/L, 12.5mg/L and 6.25mg/L at time of 60mins. Then, the solution was analysed using a u/v spectrophotometer at a wavelength of 416nm.

3.3.3 EFFECT OF pH

To investigate the effect of pH, purpurin dye (50 ml) was placed in a beaker and studied using a photolytic reactor. Experiment was conducted by varying the pH in the range (1-9). After completion of each pH, the solution was analysed using a u/v spectrophotometer at a wavelength of 416nm

3.4 EFFECT OF OPERATING PARAMETERS UNDER PHOTOCATALYSIS

During this experiment, photocatalysis treatment of purpurin dye was observed under the effect of time, nanodosage, pH and concentration. Titanium oxide was used as photocatalysts.

3.4.1 EFFECT OF TIME

The effect of contact time on the degradation of purpurin dye was investigated. Purpurin dye (50mls) containing catalyst (0.02g) was placed in a beaker and studied using a photolytic reactor for 10min, 20min, 30min, 40min and 60min. After each time completion, the mixture is filtered and the filtrate analyzed using a u/v spectrophotometer at a wavelength of 416nm.

3.4.2 EFFECT OF NANODOSAGE

The effect of the amount of titanium oxide on the degradation of purpurin dye was conducted using a photolytic reactor. This was achieved by placing purpurin dye (50mls) in a beaker with 0.02g of the catalyst and this was observed for 60mins each. After each time completion, the mixture was filtered and the filtrate analyzed using a u/v spectrophotometer at a wavelength of 416nm

3.4.3 EFFECT OF CONCENTRATION

The effect of concentration on the degradation of purpurin dye was investigated. Purpurin dye (20mls) was placed in a beaker and studied using a photolytic reactor and this was done for concentration of 100mg/L, 50mg/L, 25mg/L, 12.5mg/L and 6.25mg/L

at time of 60mins for each concentration. After time completion, the mixture was filtered and the filtrate analyzed using a u/v spectrophotometer at a wavelength of 416nm.

3.4.4 EFFECT OF pH

To investigate the effect of pH, purpurin dye (50ml) containing catalyst (0.02g) was placed in a beaker and studied using a photolytic reactor. Experiment was conducted by varying the pH in the range (1-9) with each value observed for 60mins. After each time completion, the mixture was filtered and the filtrate analysed using a u/v spectrophotometer at a wavelength of 416nm.

CHAPTER FOUR

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

4.0 PHOTOLYSIS

4.1 EFFECT OF TIME

Fig. 5 shows the effect of time on the degradation of purpurin dye solution. The %degradation increases with time and improves from 87% to 95%.

Figure 5: Effect of time on degradation of purpurin dye solution

4.1.1 EFFECT OF CONCENTRATION

Fig. 6 shows the effect of initial concentration on the degradation of purpurin dye solution. The %degradation decreases with decrease in concentration and moves from 7% to 0.5%. The %degradation obtained is lower than that obtained in photocatalytic

treatment.

Figure 6: Effect of concentration on the degradation of purpurin dye solution

4.1.2 EFFECT OF pH

Fig. 7 shows the effect of pH on the degradation of purpurin dye solution. The %degradation increases from 86.5% in the acidic medium to 95% in the basic medium. Therefore, degradation is favored in the basic medium than the acidic medium.

Figure 7: Effect of pH on the degradation of purpurin dye solution

4.2 PHOTOCATALYSIS

4.2.1 EFFECT OF TIME

Fig. 8 demonstrates the effect of contact time on the degradation of purpurin dye solution. From the graph below, it shows that an increase in time results in a higher degradation and vice versa. As a result of this, the %degradation increases from 33% to 52.5%.

Figure 8: Effect of time on photocatalytic degradation of purpurin dye solution

4.2.2 EFFECT OF NANODOSAGE

Fig. 9 shows the effect of nanodosage (0.02g) on the photocatalytic degradation of purpurin dye, observed for 60min. The degradation efficiency decreased as the dosage increases from 0.02-0.1g. Therefore, it shows that higher degradation occurs at lower nanodosage (0.02g) and improves the %degradation from 20.5% to 52.5%.

Figure 9: Effect of nanodosage on photocatalytic degradation of purpurin dye solution

4.2.3 EFFECT OF CONCENTRATION

The influence of concentration on the degradation of purpurin dye by nanocomposite was investigated by varying the concentration from 6.25mg/L to 100mg/L. Fig. 10 shows that the %degradation declines as the concentration increases from 6.25mg/L (94.5%) to 100mg/L (52.5%) when observed for 60min.

Figure 10: Effect of concentration on the photocatalytic degradation of purpurin dye solution

4.2.4 EFFECT OF pH

Fig. 11 demonstrates the effect of pH on the degradation of purpurin dye using the nanocomposite as a photocatalyst. From the graph, the %degradation increased from 39% to 59% as pH increases from 1 to 9. Therefore, the degradation of purpurin dye using the nanocomposite is favored in the basic medium

pH
Figure 11: Effect of pH on the photocatalytic degradation of purpurin dye solution

CHAPTER FIVE

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

5.1 CONCLUSION

The presence of dye in the environment often result in environmental pollution. Several methods have been employed for the removal of purpurin dye in the environment. Methods such as traditional approach (physical, chemical and biological) advanced oxidation processes and cutting oxidative techniques. In this study, the synergic effect of TiO₂ nanoparticles were used for the removal of purpurin dye. The result showed that the application of TiO₂ nanoparticles did not enhance the removal process of purpurin dye.

Hence the removal process of purpurin dye was best achieved via photocatalysis.

5.2 RECOMMENDATION

I recommend that the following should be done;

1. Degradation should be done on other dyes via photocatalysis
2. Other nanoparticles such as ZnO, AgNO₃ can also be used to treat purpurin dye
3. Other advanced oxidation process such as ultrasound, fenton e.t.c can also be explored for treatment of purpurin dye.
4. Kinetics and mechanism of degradation can also be explored.

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APPENDIX 1

PHOTOLYSIS

Table 1: Effect of Time

Time (min)	Absorbance	Initial Concentration (mg/L)	Final Concentration (mg/L)	% Degradation
10	0.030	100	13	87
20	0.028	100	12	88
30	0.025	100	10.5	89.5
40	0.022	100	9	91
60	0.018	100	7	93

Table 2: Effect of Concentration

Concentration (mg/L)	Absorbance	Initial Concentration (mg/L)	Final Concentration (mg/L)	% Degradation
100	0.018	100	7	93
50	0.011	100	3.5	96.5
25	0.009	100	2.5	97.5
12.5	0.007	100	1.5	98.5
6.25	0.004	100	0	100

Table 3: Effect of pH

Ph	Absorbance	Initial Concentration (mg/L)	Final Concentration (mg/L)	% Degradation
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1	0.031	100	13.5	86.5
3	0.028	100	12	88
5	0.024	100	10	90
7	0.018	100	7	93
9	0.014	100	5	95

APPENDIX 2

PHOTOCATALYSIS USING TITANIUM OXIDE AS PHOTOCATALYST

Table 4: Effect of Time

Time (min)	Absorbance	Initial Concentration (mg/L)	Final Concentration (mg/L)	% Degradation
10	0.138	100	67	33
20	0.130	100	63	37
30	0.125	100	60.5	39.5
40	0.112	100	54	46
60	0.099	100	47.5	52.5

Table 5: Effect of Nanodosage

Nanodosage (g)	Absorbance	Initial Concentration (mg/L)	Final Concentration (mg/L)	% Degradation
0.02	0.099	100	47.5	52.5
0.04	0.103	100	49.5	50.5
0.06	0.112	100	54	46
0.08	0.146	100	71	29
0.1	0.163	100	79.5	20.5

Table 6: Effect of pH

Ph	Absorbance	Initial Concentration (mg/L)	Final Concentration (mg/L)	% Degradation
1	0.126	100	61	39
3	0.118	100	57	43
5	0.112	100	54	46
7	0.099	100	47.5	52.5
9	0.086	100	41	59

Table 7: Effect of concentration

Concentration (mg/L)	Absorbance	Initial Concentration (mg/L)	Final Concentration (mg/L)	% Degradation
100	0.099	100	47.5	52.5
50	0.075	100	35.5	64.5
25	0.050	100	23	77
12.5	0.032	100	14	86
6.25	0.015	100	5.5	94

Figure 12: Purpurin dye solution

Figure 13: UV spectrometer